

Studies on the effect of halide ions as perturbing agents on a B-Z oscillating system with gallic acid as substrate

S. C. Pal and R. S. Banerjee*

Department of Chemistry, University College of Science, 92, Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Calcutta-700 009, India

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The effect of initial addition of chloride, bromide and iodide ions as perturbing agents on a B-Z oscillating system has been studied visually and potentiometrically side by side by batch method. Gallic acid has been used as the organic substrate, sulphuric acid as the medium, potassium bromate as the oxidizing agent and ferroin as indicator. The oscillation parameters have been determined at different halide concentrations and the difference in the role of the halide ions has been discussed in terms of FKN mechanism. A brief review on the previous works in similar systems has also been made.

Belousov-Zhabotinskii (BZ) reaction¹ is perhaps the most widely investigated oscillating chemical reaction. Different organic and inorganic substrates and different catalysts have been used in these systems. The broad mechanism of the reaction has been worked out by Field, Körös and Noyes for metal ion catalyzed systems (FKN mechanism)² and by Orban, Körös and Noyes for uncatalyzed systems (OKN mechanism)². The latter has been modified slightly by Herbine and Field². The behaviour of the B-Z systems (catalyzed and uncatalyzed) in presence of halide ions has been studied by several workers using different organic substrates.

Gallic acid³ has been very successfully used as an organic substrate by different workers in presence as also in absence of ferroin catalyst. Both batch and CSTR modes have been used. In batch method, the number of oscillations is small, however, in absence of a catalyst. In presence of ferroin, the number of oscillations is quite large. The colour changes (red to blue) are very sharp and can be easily demonstrated. In the present studies, this gallic acid-bromate-H₂SO₄-ferroin system has been subjected to initial addition of different halide ions at different concentrations, and the effects on induction period, total number of oscillations, total time of oscillation, oscillation frequency (number of oscillations per unit time) and oscillation period have been examined both visually and potentiometrically side by side. The plots of time period (as noted visually) against time also indicate the nature of the oscillations in presence of halide ions. Such perturbation studies have contributed essentially to our thorough understanding of the mechanism of bromate-driven oscillators. It may be mentioned that gallic acid was not taken up by earlier workers for studying the effect of initial addition of halide ions.

Results and Discussion

The representative potentiometric traces are shown in Figs. 1-3. The plots of induction period against the concentration of different halide ions are shown in Fig. 4. Some representative plots of oscillation period (as visually recorded) against time are shown in Figs. 5-7. The values of induction period, total number of oscillations, total time of oscillations and time period (3rd and 4th) in absence and presence of halide ions in different concentrations as recorded visually and potentiometrically are presented in Tables 1-3.

Effect on the induction period :

The induction period sharply increases with increasing concentration of added potassium chloride solution. This is evident from the plot of induction period vs concentration of chloride ions (Fig. 4 and Table 1). With increase in concentration of added bromide ions, however, there are ups and downs in induction period, and at high concentrations, it is moderately high (Fig. 4 and Table 2). The increase is not so sharp as in presence of chloride ions. Again at low concentrations of added bromide ions, induction period is less than that in absence of added bromide ions. This suggests an inducing action of bromide ions. With increase in concentration of iodide ions, induction period sharply increases and this is comparable to the effect of chloride ions (Fig. 4 and Table 3). At low concentration of iodide ions, however, a decrease in induction period indicates some inducing action of these ions.

In general, the induction periods in presence of chloride or iodide ions are much higher than the values in presence of added bromide ions.

Effect on the total number of oscillations :

In presence of chloride ions, the total number of oscilla-

Fig. 1. Potential oscillation in GA-KBrO₃-H₂SO₄-Ferroin-KCl System : (a) 0.00075 N KCl, (b) 0.00150 N KCl.

tions decreases with increasing concentrations of KCl (Table 1). The same trend is observed in presence of added bromide ions, though with some variations (Table 2). The number of oscillations remains practically same at different concentrations of iodide ions. At high concentration of iodide ions, however, the number is much less (Table 3).

Effect on the total time of oscillation (excluding induction period) :

The total time of oscillation decreases with increasing concentration of chloride ions, though with some variations (Table 1). There is no regularity, however, in case of added bromide ions. But at high concentration of bromide, it is considerably small (Table 2). In case of iodide ions also, no regularity is observed with increasing concentration of iodide ions (Table 3).

Effect on the oscillation frequency :

The number of oscillations per unit time (oscillation fre-

quency per min) increases with increasing concentration of chloride ions, becomes maximum and then decreases. In case of bromide ion addition, the changes in oscillation frequency are not regular. With increasing concentration of iodide ions, this parameter changes as in case of chloride ions.

Effect on the oscillation period :

Variation with concentration of halide ion : Strangely enough, a particular oscillation period (say 3rd or 4th) decreases in presence of chloride ions at low concentration. At high concentrations of chloride ions, however, the oscillation period is virtually the same as that in absence of chloride ions (Table 1). With increasing concentration of bromide ions, there is no regularity in oscillation period. Especially at the KBr concentrations of 0.00214 N and 0.00535 N, the 3rd and 4th oscillation periods and at 0.000535 N and 0.001605 N, the 4th oscillation periods are off the trend. But it is always higher than that in absence of added bro-

Fig. 2. Potential oscillation in GA-KBrO₃-H₂SO₄-Ferroun-KBr system (a) 0.00107 N KBr, (b) 0.02020 N KBr

Fig. 3. Potential oscillation in GA-KBrO₃-H₂SO₄-Ferroun-KI system (a) 0.0010 N KI, (b) 0.0030 N KI

vide ion (Table 2). The oscillation period increases, however, with increasing concentration of iodide (Table 3). In all cases, the other oscillation periods (other than 3rd and 4th) also have the same trend.

Variation with time A plot of oscillation period vs time reveals marked ups and downs in its value specially at high concentration of chloride ion. At low concentrations of chlo-

Fig. 4. Effect of halide ion on induction period in B-Z system GA-KBrO₃-H₂SO₄-Ferroun effect of (●) Cl⁻, (○) Br⁻, (Δ) I⁻

Fig. 5. Effect of chloride ion on time period in B-Z system GA-KBrO₃-H₂SO₄-Ferroun for (●) 0.00075 N, (○) 0.001 N, (▲) 0.00125 N, (Δ) 0.0015 N KCl

Fig. 6. Effect of bromide ion on time period in B-Z system GA-KBrO₃-H₂SO₄-Ferroun for (○) 0.00107 N, (Δ) 0.001605 N, (●) 0.01010 N, (▲) 0.02020 N KBr

Fig. 7. Effect of iodide ion on time period in B-Z system GA-KBrO₃-H₂SO₄-Ferrioin for (O) 0.0010 N, (Δ) 0.0015 N, (●) 0.0020 N, (▲) 0.0025 N, (◊) 0.0030 N KI

ride ions, there is more or less a gradual increase in time-period as expected for a damped oscillation in batch mode (Fig. 5). Similar plots in case of added bromide ions show irregularities in the beginning specially at high concentrations of added bromide ions. In the later stages, there is a gradual increase in time period (Fig. 6). In case of iodide ions, oscillation period decreases at first (with minor variations) and then gradually increases (Fig. 7).

Other observations

(i) Visible and potentiometric oscillations started and stopped simultaneously irrespective of the nature of the halide ions added.

(ii) The representative potentiometric traces (Figs. 1-3) show that the amplitude of oscillation is quite large in all concentrations of chloride ions. It is not always high, however, in presence of added bromide ions. In case of the highest concentration of bromide ions, the amplitude is moderate. In presence of iodide ions also, the amplitude is not always high, but rather low at high iodide concentrations.

(iii) In absence of (added) halide ions, the amplitude of oscillation gradually decreases before the oscillations stop. But in presence of chloride ions, rather abrupt deadening of oscillation takes place. No such abrupt deadening of oscillation is observed even when the bromide or iodide concentration is high (Figs. 1-3).

(iv) When the concentration of KCl is changed from 0.00150 to 0.00175 N, oscillation does not occur (observation made upto 32 min). On the other hand, when the added bromide ion concentration is changed from 0.0202 to 0.0303 N, there is no oscillation (observation made upto 14 min).

A change in concentration of KI from 0.0040 to 0.0045 N leads to cessation of oscillation (observation continued upto 43 min).

Mechanism and the role of halide ions :

The skeleton FKN mechanism² may be briefly discussed in terms of processes A, B and C below.

Process A

Process B

Process C

When [Br⁻] is large, [HBrO₂] is small and the system is in a reduced state. When [Br⁻] is small, [HBrO₂] is large and the system is in an oxidized state. The transition occurs near a critical value of [Br⁻]. Whenever [Br⁻] passes through [Br⁻]_{crit}, [HBrO₂] changes almost discontinuously. It is this almost discontinuous change in [HBrO₂] that generates the relaxation oscillations.

Gallic acid (GA, the substrate in the present study) has been found to be easily oxidized by BrO₃⁻ in acidic media. Extensive studies by Jwo and Chang³, and Liu and Scott³ indicate that the following steps are likely to occur (as modification to the the original OKN mechanism²):

Table 1. Study of the effect of chloride ions on B-Z systemGA = 0.0235 M, KBrO₃ = 0.0666 M, H₂SO₄ = 2.048 N, Ferriin = 8.3 × 10⁻⁵ M, Temp = 33.5 ± 0.5°

Concn of KCl soln N	Induction period s		No of oscillations		Total time of oscillations* s		Oscillation frequency per min		3rd oscillation period s		4th oscillation period s	
	Vis	Pot	Vis	Pot	Vis	Pot	Vis	Pot	Vis	Pot	Vis	Pot
Nil	116	120	52	52	2254	2256	1384	1382	38	36	46	44
0.00050	189	192	44	44	1818	1800	1452	1466	24	24	25	26
0.00075	236	240	32	32	1278	1272	1502	1509	26	26	30	28
0.00100	321	322	27	27	1190	1190	1361	1361	32	32	28	28
0.00125	520	518	28	28	1525	1524	1101	1102	37	37	40	40
0.00150	1040	1040	23	23	1383	1368	0998	1009	41	42	42	43
0.00175	No oscillation											

*Excluding induction period

Table 2. Study of the effect of bromide ions on B-Z systemGA = 0.0235 M, KBrO₃ = 0.0666 M, H₂SO₄ = 2.048 N, Ferriin = 8.3 × 10⁻⁵ M, Temp = 31 ± 1°

Concn of KBr soln N	Induction period s		No of oscillations		Total time of oscillations* s		Oscillation frequency per min		3rd oscillation period s		4th oscillation period s	
	Vis	Pot	Vis	Pot	Vis	Pot	Vis	Pot	Vis	Pot	Vis	Pot
Nil	170	164	52	–	2395	–	1303	–	34	36	31	30
0.000535	168	168	46	46	2380	2376	1159	1162	54	54	88	86
0.001070	98	96	44	44	1892	1896	1395	1392	42	44	52	50
0.001605	104	108	53	53	2873	2866	1107	1110	53	48	81	82
0.002140	125	126	49	49	2971	2970	0990	0990	85	84	85	84
0.002675	108	108	42	42	2042	2040	1234	1235	51	50	50	50
0.003210	85	84	39	39	1701	1692	1376	1383	55	55	55	54
0.004280	85	84	38	38	1841	1836	1238	1242	61	62	65	64
0.005350	118	120	38	38	1891	1896	1206	1203	86	84	82	82
0.010100	203	200	29	29	1676	1608	1038	1082	50	50	39	37
0.020200	303	300	14	14	687	640	1223	1313	43	42	48	46
0.030300	No oscillation											

*Excluding induction period

where, P₁ is 5-carboxy-3-hydroxyorthoquinone, a quinone derivative of GA.

The last step can act as a suitable source of bromide ion. The product P₁ in its turn may react with the radical species BrO₂[•] to provide the 'missing link' in the autocatalytic cycle, when the external catalyst is absent. The step BrO₂[•] + ferriin (or Ce³⁺) + H⁺ → HBrO₂ + ferriin (or Ce⁴⁺) in presence of catalyst (in FKN scheme) may be replaced by BrO₂[•] + P₁ → HBrO₂ + R[•] in absence of catalyst. The quinone thus plays the role of the traditional one-electron transfer catalyst.

The effect of addition of halide ions on B-Z systems has been studied by various workers and their role has been mainly explained in terms of FKN mechanism. A brief review of the previous work is desirable in each case.

Role of added chloride ions : In an early study, Zhabotinskii¹ reported that addition of 'small amounts' of KCl caused permanent suppression of oscillation. Field *et al*² observed the same while trying to do potentiometric measurements with a KCl salt-bridge. No explanation, however, was given. Janjic *et al*⁴ reported that chloride completely inhibited oscillations when malonic acid was replaced by acetylacetone. Jacobs and Epstein⁴ (who used malonic acid as the organic substrate and cerium ions as catalyst) were the first to investigate the effect of chloride ions in some details. They noted that chloride ion lengthened the induction period and claimed that the induced inhibition was a transient phenomenon. They observed that the induction period could be divided into two parts. The length of the

Table 3. Study of the effect of iodide ions on B-Z system

GA = 0.0235 M, KBrO₃ = 0.0666 M, H₂SO₄ = 2.048 N, Ferroin = 8.3 × 10⁻⁵ M, Temp. = 33 ± 1°

Concn. of KI soln. N	Induction period s		No. of oscillations		Total time of oscillations* s		Oscillation frequency per min		3rd oscillation period s		4th oscillation period s	
	Vis.	Pot.	Vis.	Pot.	Vis.	Pot.	Vis.	Pot.	Vis.	Pot.	Vis.	Pot.
Nil	122	120	57	—	3210	—	1.065	—	68	66	—	56
0.0005	100	96	54	54	2050	1980	1.580	1.636	30	28	32	30
0.0010	122	122	60	60	2178	2118	1.653	1.700	30	32	29	28
0.0015	148	144	56	56	2022	1944	1.662	1.728	39	40	44	44
0.0020	202	192	55	55	1805	1752	1.828	1.884	46	48	48	50
0.0025	300	288	62	62	2280	2220	1.632	1.676	56	58	50	48
0.0030	370	360	57	57	2280	2208	1.500	1.549	88	84	89	86
0.0035	805	792	43	43	1980	1920	1.303	1.344	94	96	—	—
0.0040	1380	1344	35	35	2016	1944	1.042	1.080	103	106	197	192
0.0045	No oscillation											

*Excluding induction period.

first part varied significantly with the chloride ion concentration, while the second part was relatively invariant. The general characteristics of the second part resembled those of the unperturbed induction period. They found that for $[Cl^-]_0 \leq 10^{-4} M$, no observable inhibition was produced. For $[Cl^-]_0 \geq 2 \times 10^{-3} M$, oscillation was totally suppressed. According to their suggestion, Cl⁻ ion operates by disrupting the autocatalytic formation of bromous acid, HBrO₂, through the reaction,

and thus competes with both bromide and bromate ions for the bromous acid,

The bromous acid will be principally consumed by chloride (thermodynamically favoured) so long as

$$[Cl^-] > [Cl^-]_{crit} = \frac{K_2}{K_1} [Br^-] + \frac{K_3}{K_1} [BrO_3^-]$$

Oscillations start after the Cl⁻ ions are converted (through HOCl, HClO₂ and ClO₂ as intermediates) to ClO₃⁻ ion (whose addition has no effect on the reaction) through several steps. The overall reaction is

The possibility also exists that some or all the chloride is ultimately incorporated into an organic form.

Muranyi and Försterling⁴, however, reported chloride-induced oscillations (high frequency, small amplitude) at high malonic acid/bromate ratio in presence of added chloride in a cerium-catalyzed B-Z system. Surprisingly, the oscillations started immediately after the addition of the catalyst if chloride ion concentration was within a certain range. The oscillations were considered to be non-bromide controlled and explained by the 'Radicalator' model. They assumed control by a synergetic process involving both chloride ions and malonyl radical.

Rastogi and Misra⁴ observed that the oscillations (cerium ion catalyzed malonic acid system) were quenched on addition of Cl⁻ ions during the oscillatory phase when Cl⁻ ion concentration was $5.73 \times 10^{-4} M$. On adding a moderate amount of Cl⁻ ion during oscillation, the amplitude was shortened. On increasing the amount, the oscillations were quenched for a longer period and even permanently. When Cl⁻ ion was added initially, the onset time was lengthened, in agreement with the observation of Jacobs and Epstein, and oscillations continued upto the case when $[Cl^-]_0 \approx 1.14 \times 10^{-3} M$. The experimental phase-plane plots confirmed the observations and showed (i) how the quenching vector moved away from the limit cycle and then fell back on the limit cycle when the oscillations were interrupted for a while and (ii) how the quenching vector moved away from the limit cycle and fell back on the stable focus. Numerical simulation for the oscillatory behaviour on addition of Cl⁻ ion during oscillation was attempted by including the reaction, $HBrO_2 + Cl^- + H^+ \longrightarrow HOBr + HOCl$ in the model. Computer results were in agreement with the experimental

behaviour. Computer calculations for the onset time when Cl^- ions were added initially showed that oscillations stopped only when Cl^- ion concentration reached $\sim 10^{-3} M$.

Körös *et al.*⁴ observed that when some uncatalyzed bromate oscillators were perturbed with chloride ions ($\sim 10^{-3} M$), the number of oscillations increased from a few tens to 250–300, and both amplitude and time period decreased considerably.

Kurin-Csorgei *et al.*⁴ used *para*-substituted phenol derivatives as the organic substrate in uncatalyzed B-Z system and observed regular oscillations, twin oscillations (which changed to regular oscillations with time), oscillation bursts and lastly quenching of oscillations when Cl^- ion concentration was increased from 1.7×10^{-3} to $2.1 \times 10^{-3} M$. They also observed temperature-triggered oscillations. Solutions which did not show oscillations in presence of a certain concentration of chloride ion, started oscillating when the temperature was increased. The transitions were temperature-reversible and when an oscillating system was cooled, cessation of oscillation occurred at the same temperature. Hysteresis was not observable. Moreover, they reported that in presence of Cl^- ions, the number of oscillations increased and the amplitude decreased, indicating that the amount of initial reactants and important intermediates consumed in a single oscillatory step was less than that in unperturbed system. That the effect of initially added Cl^- ions persisted for sometime indicated that these ions are not immediately oxidized to the chlorate and organically bound chlorine (forming C–Cl bonds) by the bromate. Chlorate and organically bound chlorine belong to non-recycling species, i.e. they are sinks for Cl^- ions. They also reported that the critical Cl^- ion concentration above which oscillations terminated or did not set in when added initially, vary between 6×10^{-4} and $1.3 \times 10^{-3} M$ depending on the composition of the B-Z system.

The present B-Z system using gallic acid as substrate is similar to those of Jacobs and Epstein, and Rastogi and Misra, who used malonic acid. A similar mechanism is likely to operate here. The Cl^- ions compete with Br^- and BrO_2^- ions for HBrO_2 and Cl^- ions are ultimately converted to non-recycling ClO_3^- ions and/or organic form involving C–Cl bond. After the removal of Cl^- ions, oscillations take place as usual. At a concentration of $1.75 \times 10^{-3} M$ (a value comparable to those reported by the above authors), oscillations were permanently quenched. The present system is very sensitive to Cl^- ions, as the steep curve showing variation of induction period with Cl^- ion concentration will show (Fig. 4). The effect is also reflected in the decrease in total number of oscillations and total time of oscillation with in-

crease in Cl^- ion concentration. The induction period can be divided into two parts. The first part is more or less invariant and the U-shaped potential drop during this period is observed in absence of Cl^- ions also. The second part increases with increase in concentration of Cl^- ions and the potentiometric trace is more or less horizontal during this period. In Jacob's system, however, the first part is variable and the second part relatively invariant. The reason for the difference is not clear to us. It is also not clear why a particular period (say 3rd or 4th) decreases in presence of Cl^- ions at low Cl^- ion concentration but increases as Cl^- ion concentration is increased or why there should be marked ups and downs in oscillation period with time specially at high concentration of Cl^- ions. The observations that the oscillations take place through a large range of potential and there is an abrupt deadening of oscillation remain unexplained.

Role of added bromide ions : Blandamer and Roberts⁵ and Treindl and Drojakova⁵ studied the effect of addition of Br^- ion on B-Z system. It was observed by the former workers that when the B-Z oscillating reaction (using malonic acid as the substrate and cerium ions as catalyst) was perturbed by rapid addition of bromide ions, the oscillations disappeared but then recovered. The time for recovery depends on the extent of concentration perturbation, but the new frequency and amplitude of oscillation closely resemble the frequency and amplitude before perturbation and the reaction follows a limit cycle type behaviour.

In B-Z system, bromide ion has been considered as the control intermediate in FKN mechanism² and the result of Br^- ion addition has been explained by Blandamer and Roberts⁵ as due to a shift of control of the oscillator to process A of the mechanism until the Br^- ion added is removed through several steps.

Li and Huang⁵ reported high frequency, low frequency and dual frequency oscillations (i.e. both high and low frequency oscillations with a transition period between them) in a ferriin-catalyzed B-Z system with 3,4-dihydroxybenzoic acid as the organic substrate (using a bromide ion sensitive electrode) at high low and moderate concentrations of bromide respectively. Both high and low frequency oscillations were inhibited by acrylamide, a well-known radical scavenger, indicating that the oscillations occurred by a free-radical mechanism. When $[\text{Br}^-]_0$ was $\leq 2.3 \times 10^{-3} M$, only low frequency oscillations occurred. When $[\text{Br}^-]_0$ was $\geq 2.9 \times 10^{-3} M$, only high frequency oscillations were observed, indicating that they were induced by the bromide ions. When $2.3 \times 10^{-3} M < [\text{Br}^-]_0 < 2.9 \times 10^{-3} M$, the system displayed a dual frequency oscillation with a transition period between

high and low frequency oscillations. The oscillation was completely inhibited when $[Br^-]_0$ was $> 6.0 \times 10^{-3} M$. The induction period of the low frequency oscillation increased slightly with increasing $[Br^-]_0$, whereas the transition period decreased with increasing $[Br^-]_0$. It was also concluded that the low frequency oscillation was given by the organic acid (H_2A) and the high frequency oscillation by the bromo-derivative of the acid. Kurin-Csörgei *et al.*⁴ observed temperature-triggered oscillation in uncatalyzed B-Z systems (using *para*-substituted phenols) when perturbed with chloride ions but not with bromide ions.

In the present studies with platinum electrode, oscillations were not observed when $[Br^-]_0$ is $3.03 \times 10^{-2} N$. No dual frequency oscillation was noticed and there were ups and downs in the induction period. The total number of oscillations decreased with increasing Br^- ion concentration. No regularity was observed in total time of oscillation or a particular oscillation period. A plot of time period vs time shows increase, decrease and then gradual increase. FKN mechanism is likely to operate here involving a shift of control to process A. The lack of regularity in oscillation parameters is perhaps not unexpected in view of the fact that Br^- ion is generally the control intermediate in B-Z systems and in the present case these particular ions are being added from outside.

Role of added iodide ions : Jacobs and Epstein⁴ observed that I^- ions caused inhibition qualitatively similar to the chloride inhibition. Kaner and Epstein⁶, however, reported a variety of interesting phenomena in a bromate-cerium-malonic acid system, depending on the initial I^- ion concentration. At moderately high and low $[I^-]_0$, the onset of oscillations is delayed, while very high $[I^-]_0$ ($> 6 \times 10^{-3} M$) totally suppresses oscillation. In an intermediate range, i.e. $10^{-3} M < [I^-]_0 < 3 \times 10^{-3} M$, a new type of induced 'small oscillations' appears almost immediately. These small oscillations end abruptly and a second induction period ensues. This period concludes with the sudden initiation of the 'normal' B-Z oscillations. As $[I^-]_0$ is increased, the number of small oscillations increases and the second induction period decreases. When $[I^-]_0$ reaches $3 \times 10^{-3} M$, the second induction period disappears and the small oscillations grow directly into the normal oscillations. Kaner and Epstein suggested that when $[I^-]_0 < \text{total cerium content}$, the principal reaction is oxidation of I^- to I_2 by Ce^{IV} ,

Thus the mechanism of inhibition is different from that due to Cl^- ions, where no such direct reduction of Ce^{IV} takes place. They also suggested that the induced small oscilla-

tions were driven by glyoxalic acid (GOA) formed by the reaction of iodomalonic acid with BrO_3^- . Iodate ion, which is the ultimate fate of iodide ion has, however, a mild inhibiting effect (difference from chlorate ion).

Körös and Varga⁶ made a quantitative study in the manganese ion-catalyzed system. Varga *et al.*⁶ extended these studies to uncatalyzed systems and found that addition of a few times $10^{-3} M$ iodide increased the number of oscillations significantly if the substrate was a *para*-substituted phenol derivative. Ruoff *et al.*⁶ found on using 4-[2-(methylamino)propyl]phenol, i.e. HMP as substrate in an uncatalyzed system that the number of oscillations increased dramatically to 30–120 from 3–6 (I^- -free system). The mixing order of the reacting solutions is important. Again, at certain initial compositions, a temporary bistability was found between an oscillatory state and an oxidized steady state. Ruoff *et al.*⁶ interpreted the effects of I^- addition by assuming that HOI (an expected product of the oxidation of I^- by BrO_3^-) oxidizes the HMP 'aliphatic side-chain' to yield an intermediate that reacts very rapidly with $HOBr$ so as to enhance Br^- production. This leads to less consumption of reactants in a cycle and increased number and lower amplitude of oscillations. They also argued that reduction of HOI by HMP prevented the irreversible removal of iodine from the oscillatory mechanism by its oxidation to IO_3^- by BrO_3^- .

Györgyi *et al.*⁶ made an alternative suggestion that HOI iodinate HMP on the 'benzene ring' and the products react with $HBrO_2$, regenerating HOI and inhibiting the $HBrO_2$ oxidative autocatalysis. This decreases the amplitude of each oxidative excursion and conserves the principal reactants so as to increase the number of oscillations.

Li and Huang⁵ reported high frequency oscillation in presence of bromide with 3,4-dihydroxybenzoic acid as the substrate in a ferroin-catalyzed system. No such high frequency oscillation was detected by them when Br^- ions were replaced by I^- ions. Uncatalyzed system also did not show oscillation no matter how the I^- ion concentration was adjusted.

Kurin-Csörgei *et al.*⁴ could not observe any temperature-triggered oscillation in uncatalyzed B-Z systems using *para*-substituted phenols when perturbed with I^- ions (though observed with Cl^- ions).

In the present studies with gallic acid as the substrate in the ferroin-catalyzed B-Z system, the change in induction period with change in concentration of I^- ions is quite sharp, as in case of Cl^- ions. But the total number of oscillations or total time of oscillations is not closely related to the I^- ion concentration (different from the case of Cl^- ions). No oscillation was observed when $[I^-]_0 = 4.5 \times 10^{-3} M$. This

figure is comparable to that reported by other workers for similar systems. Dual frequency oscillations, however, were not observed in the present system. The inhibition produced by I^- ions can be explained by considering that the principal reaction is oxidation of I^- to I_2 by ferriin, thus disrupting process C of skeleton FKN mechanism,

The reduction potentials of ferriin-ferroin system ($E^0 = 1.18$ V) and $1/2 I_2-I^-$ system ($E^0 = 0.62$ V) support this assumption. The ultimate fate of I^- ion, however, is IO_3^- ion. This suggestion is along the line suggested by Kaner and Epstein⁶ in cerium-catalyzed system.

Thus the values of the induction period, the potentiometric traces and the nature of the variation of time period with time as also other factors mentioned above, all indicate that the roles played by added chloride, bromide and iodide ions are altogether different.

Experimental

A weighed amount of gallic acid was mixed with requisite amounts of water and solutions of sulphuric acid, ferroin, potassium halide and potassium bromate. The reaction was triggered by the addition of the last reagent. The solutions for different sets were so prepared and mixed that the concentrations shown in Tables 1-3 were the concentrations in the medium at the start. No reagent was added during the run of the reaction so as to work in batch and to obtain a closed system in the thermodynamic sense. The reaction mixture was slowly stirred at a fixed rate with the help of a magnetic stirrer. The potential oscillations in the system were recorded with the help of a bright platinum electrode dipped in the reaction mixture and a saturated calomel electrode (reference electrode), connected by an ammonium nitrate salt-bridge. The two electrodes were connected to a $x-t$ strip chart recorder. The oscillations were also simultaneously recorded visually from the sharp colour change from red to blue. As the oscillation periods were of the order of minutes, the oscillation parameters could be visually noted quite easily and precisely and could also be compared side by

side with those obtained from potentiometric observation.

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